

The Problem of Developing Children's Physical Qualities Through Table Tennis

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Abstract: The article studies the issues of creating conditions that meet the requirements of the time for the development of general and special physical qualities, as well as technical and tactical training of table tennis athletes and regular participation in mass sports, developing physical qualities and strengthening confidence in their capabilities.

Keywords: table tennis, physical qualities, athletes, sports, healthy lifestyle, speed, movement, special tactical training.

INTRODUCTION

Today, physical education and sports are becoming one of the most priority areas of the world community. Among the sports, gymnastics serves as the main tool in the process of physical education of children. Within the framework of the broad political and social reforms being carried out in the life of our country, extensive work is being carried out to improve the quality of educational and upbringing activities in preschool education, to create advanced pedagogical, psychological and information and communication technologies and necessary conditions for the educational process.

Today, the fundamental reforms in our political, social, economic, and spiritual and educational life being carried out in our Republic under the leadership of our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev encourage us to solve extremely important tasks, such as organizing educational and sports and health work in a completely new content, form and means, and to fully use the unique opportunities created for them, raising our growing youth as worthy children of the Fatherland.

In order to maintain and further improve their position on international sports arenas, coaches and athletes need to use the latest scientific developments in biomechanics, physiology, and other disciplines relevant to the system of athlete training in practice, and to regularly improve their own system of advanced training methods based on the generalization of the experience of the world's strongest tennis players.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Any state that thinks about its future pays great attention, first of all, to the education of youth. Physical training is a very important part of the training process, it is the process of educating the physical qualities of athletes. Physical training is a multi-year pedagogical process. It is aimed at developing general and special physical abilities of those involved, improving

important vital motor skills, strengthening functional capabilities and strengthening health. Physical fitness is a product of the physical training process.

The main task of physical training is determined by the constant increase in functional capabilities, which ensures the dynamics of the development of physical qualities. At the same time, it is to gradually bring those involved to intensive and large-scale training and competition loads that ensure the increase in special working capacity and the achievement of high sports results. Physical training is closely related to other aspects of athlete training. Highly developed speed, strength, agility, flexibility and endurance remain the main condition for mastering sports techniques and tactics. At the same time, solving physical training tasks leads to the formation of important psychological and moral-will qualities.

Physical training consists of general and special training. General physical training is aimed at ensuring a high level of development of physical qualities, creating a functional-physical basis for proper physical development and comprehensive physical fitness.

In the process of general physical training, the following issues are solved:

- ✓ comprehensive physical development of those involved;
- ✓ strengthening health;
- ✓ increasing functional capabilities;
- ✓ increasing sports-related work capacity;
- ✓ developing basic physical qualities;
- ✓ improving motor skills and competencies important for life.

Special physical training is aimed at developing special physical qualities and achieving a high level of improvement in the functioning of the functional systems of the body. The solution of these goals is the main condition for achieving high sports results. Therefore, it occupies a key place in the system of training highly qualified athletes.

Special physical training is aimed at solving the following tasks:

Identification of specific motor qualities;

- ✓ Development of endurance specific to the sport;
- ✓ Improvement of strength-to-weight endurance, taking into account the characteristics of the sport;

Improving aerobic-anaerobic performance. Special physical training serves as the physiological basis for achieving high sports results in practice.

General physical training is of great importance in the initial stages of long-term training, especially during the period of working with children and adolescents. At this time, it is necessary to create a foundation for subsequent specialized work. With the fulfillment of this task, general physical training gives way to special physical training.

The sequential implementation of physical training is explained by the fact that it is divided into several stages that are closely related to the periods of formation of a young athlete. From general physical training, the athlete gradually moves to the stage of formation of the direction, and from there to the stages of the highest development of special movement qualities. The stage of general physical training lasts from the beginning of training to 12 years of age, the second stage falls on adolescence, and the third stage falls on youth.

The first stage is a very favorable period for the development of the main characteristics of the athlete - speed, agility and flexibility.

In the second stage, there are favorable opportunities for the use of sufficiently intensive

exercises. This provides a specialized effect on the development of physical qualities. In the third stage, physical training becomes highly specialized.

The functional capabilities of the youth organism allow the use of large loads in terms of volume and intensity.

The physical fitness of an athlete is associated with his sports specialization, and the formation of his improvement is often associated with a special style of training and a sports calendar plan. Tennis players or athletes involved in other sports can also have several training sessions during the day. They are divided into main and additional training sessions. In the main training sessions, the main tasks of the day are usually solved, problems related to technical and tactical training, and in the additional, in which the loads are planned more broadly with their entire being. The following tasks can be solved in additional training:

- ✓ preparing the athlete's body to solve the main tasks;
- ✓ recovery activities after the main training;
- ✓ re-improvement of the tasks in the main training in order to increase the effectiveness of the training;
- ✓ solving tasks that are independent, different from the tasks of the main training.

Typically, highly qualified tennis players conduct two to three training sessions during the day.

The first is done before breakfast, the second between breakfast and lunch, and the third between lunch and dinner. The first training session for professional athletes coincides with the "morning physical education" period of ordinary people in terms of time.

CONCLUSION

In addition to the tasks of simply waking up from sleep and increasing muscle tone assigned to "physical education", athletes must solve the problems of a stagnant, stiff body after active motor loads the previous day and a night's sleep.

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